

New Ways, New Sounds. The Sonic Rite of Sikh Nagar Kirtan in Italy

THEA TIRAMANI

Abstract

This paper focuses on the study of sounds in Sikh nagar kirtan (religious processions) in Italy. Drawing on specific Italian case studies, it aims to describe the structure of these processions – with particular attention to sound – and to investigate their functions and meanings. In the diaspora, nagar kirtan serves to strengthen the sense of belonging to Sikhism and to foster a feeling of *communitas* among the faithful. The procession becomes a vehicle for collective memory, even for those who may not share a direct or personal one. At the same time, the nagar kirtan allows Sikhs to be recognized by Italian society, asserting their visibility and seeking acknowledgement. In this sense, the procession becomes an opportunity for community members to build bridges, establish connections, and engage in dialogue with the broader society in which they live. This essay argues that music plays a key role in the evolving relationship between the Sikh community and the Italian public. The strategic choice of procession routes, the selection of musical repertoires, and the inclusion of various ancillary elements reflect a deliberate effort to balance internal community needs with the goal of engaging and educating the wider public. *Nagar kirtan* not only highlights the devotion of the Sikh community but also expresses its commitment to fostering understanding and connection with the broader citizenry – through and especially by means of sound.

Nuove strade, nuovi suoni. Il rito sonoro dei nagar kirtan sikh in Italia. Questo saggio si concentra sullo studio dei suoni nei nagar kirtan (cortei religiosi) sikh in Italia. A partire da casi specifici di studio italiani si intende descrivere – con attenzione ai suoni – la struttura dei cortei religiosi. I nagar kirtan Sikh in diaspora assumono il compito di rafforzare il senso di appartenenza al sikhismo e permettono ai fedeli di sentirsi *communitas*. La processione diventa portatrice di una memoria collettiva anche per coloro che potrebbero non averne una condivisa. Allo stesso modo, il nagar kirtan permette ai sikh di essere riconosciuti dagli abitanti

del tessuto cittadino, rivendicando visibilità e riconoscimento. In questo senso il nagar kirtan può essere un'occasione per i membri della comunità di costruire ponti e legami con il luogo in cui vivono, e di dialogare con esso.

Questo saggio mira a dimostrare come nelle dinamiche – in continua evoluzione – tra la comunità sikh e la comunità italiana la musica abbia un ruolo fondamentale. La scelta strategica dei percorsi del corteo, le selezioni musicali e l'inclusione di vari elementi accessori alla processione riflettono uno sforzo consapevole per bilanciare le esigenze interne della comunità con l'obiettivo di coinvolgere ed educare il pubblico più ampio. Il nagar kirtan non solo evidenzia la devozione della comunità sikh, ma esprime anche il suo impegno a promuovere la comprensione e la connessione con il resto della cittadinanza anche e soprattutto attraverso il suono.

1. Field research

This essay is part of a broader research project that began in 2014¹ and was first developed in my Master's thesis,² then expand in my Ph.D. dissertation.³ The research explores various aspects of Sikh musical life in different Italian communities, particularly in Northern Italy,⁴ with a focus on the new generations of musicians and music users, and their positioning in relation to previous generations and the wider global Sikh musical landscape.

Music is a constitutive element of Sikh religious rite, both in India and in the diaspora, and is primarily expressed through the practice of *kirtan*, or devotional singing. In *kirtan* performances – now most carried out with voices, *harmonium* and *tabla*⁵ – musicians set to music the sacred words, the *shabad*, written in the *Guru Granth Sahib*, the Holy Book,⁶ giving voice to the teachings of the Sikh Gurus and other authors included in the scripture.

In the diaspora, the religious repertoire is almost exclusively confined to the *Gurdwaras*, the sikh temple – about 40 in Italy⁷ – where the *sangat*, the community of believ-

¹ The research is part of the investigation into migration realities in the Cremona territory, led and coordinated by Fulvia Caruso in collaboration with a group of students from the Department of Musicology and Cultural Heritage at the University of Pavia. Launched in 2015 and focused on the Cremona territory, the Migrating project had three main centers of interest: music and religion, music in reception centers, and the relationship with the music of the younger generations placed in the Italian school context (see Caruso 2022).

² “Competence and Aesthetics in Contemporary Sikh *Kirtan*. A study from the *Gurdwara* of Pessina Cremonese”. Thesis discussion on December 10, 2015, at the Department of Musicology and Cultural Heritage, University of Pavia.

³ “Sikh Devotional Music in Italy. Belonging, Positioning and Creativity among First and Second Generations”. Thesis discussion on July 22, 2021, at the Department of Musicology and Cultural Heritage, University of Pavia.

⁴ I concentrated mainly on the study of the communities between the provinces of Bergamo, Brescia, Cremona, Piacenza, Parma and Reggio Emilia. Then, more sporadically, I followed events related to the realities around Bolzano, Modena, Arezzo, Rome and Reggio Calabria.

⁵ For more information on the development of Sikh music from its origins to the present see Khalsa 2014 and Cassio 2015 and 2023 and for the music in diaspora see Kaur 2018, Khabra 2012, Townsend 2018.

⁶ The last and final Guru for Sikhs. He is metaphorically considered a living Guru and is subject to specific rites.

⁷ For more information about Sikh in Italy and Italian *Gurdwaras* see Denti, Ferrari, Perocco 2005, and Bertolani 2013, 2018 and 2020.

ers, gathers on weekends or during special holidays. There is, however, one key occasion when the sound of *kirtan* leaves the walls of the *Gurdwara*, and the *Guru Granth Sahib* is taken outside: the *nagar kirtan*, a religious procession held to commemorate foundational events in Sikh history.

Over the course of my research, I had the opportunity to attend many of these springtime processions. In 2019, marking the 550th anniversary of the birth of Guru Nanak, the founder of Sikhism, I decided to systematically follow as many *nagar kirtan* processions as possible throughout Italy.⁸

2. A sensorial immersion in the *nagar kirtan* of Brescia

April 20, 2019. Brescia.⁹

It is 10 a.m. on a warm, sunny spring day. I know I am early: *Departure at 12 o'clock* in Punjabi is the Italian equivalent of *maybe we'll start at 2 o'clock*, following a time zone that is entirely subjective. Last week, I attended the procession in Cremona on Saturday and the one in Rome on Sunday, while the week before I was in Bergamo, in a cold downpour. Between March, April, May, and early June, I attended several processions held to celebrate Vaisakhi: the anniversary of the founding of the *khalsa*, the community of baptized, for the Sikhs, the beginning of the solar new year for the Hindus, and a great spring festival across India. Today's event has been described me by devotees as "the most beautiful procession in Italy". For the occasion, I decided to wear my red and gold *chunni*,¹⁰ which I bought in an Indian shop in Palermo and which attracted the interest of many women last week: *Ehe chitho lai tusi? Both sona hè!*¹¹ Today is also the only day when I don't have to coordinate a team of Sikh and/or Italian friends I've asked to document other processions taking place simultaneously across the country: Brescia has the exclusive, Sikh worshippers from across Northern Italy, and beyond, will be here.

In the parking lot of the shopping center, near the starting point of the procession, buses from different cities begin to arrive. Punjabi speeches blend with conversations in Italian accents from Brescia, Bergamo, Rome, and Florence – accents that young Sikhs have now fully acquired. I follow the colorful crowd of devotees and catch sight of the first food stalls. I realize I've reached the meeting point, in an area outside the historic

⁸ I documented *nagar kirtan* performed in Cremona (04/2014; 04/2017; 04/2018; 07/2019; 10/2019), Cortemaggiore (04/2015), Martignana di Po (06/2018); Bergamo (04/2019); Rome (04/2019); Brescia (04/2019); Bolzano (04/2019); Reggio Calabria (04/2019); Fiorenzuola d'Arda (05/2019); Pontinia (05/2019); Casalmaggiore (05/2019); Solarolo Rainerio (09/2019); Modena (10/2019); Fondi (10/2019).

⁹ Brescia is a municipality in northern Italy with a population of almost 200,000. It is the second largest municipality in the Lombardy region by population, after Milan, and is one of the 20 most populous municipalities in Italy.

¹⁰ The headscarf used to cover the head during the procession or to enter to the temple.

¹¹ *Where did you buy it? How beautiful it is!*

FIGURE 1. A *dhol* player. *Nagar kirtan* in Brescia, April 20, 2019. Photo by the author.

center of Brescia, though not quite in the suburbs. Punjabi pop music blares from loudspeakers mounted on pick-up trucks and from amplifiers in the trunks of cars (Fig. 1).

I also heard a sound I had never encountered before in a procession: the *dhol*,¹² the percussion instrument used in *bhangra*,¹³ played by a young man who was exchanging a few words with others unloading huge cartons of mango juice from a van. Food is generously distributed, Punjabi music grows louder in the forecourt, and *dhadi*¹⁴ and *kirtaniya*¹⁵ begin their performances on the floats. No one seems impatient with the long wait, everyone enjoys the festive atmosphere. Devotees chat, reconnect, and get to know each other. They have come from Italy, Switzerland, Spain, and England.

A sudden shift in the crowd signals the arrival of the float from the *Gurdwara* with the *Guru Granth Sahib*. It is richly decorated with flowers and fabrics, Sikh flags, *Ik Onkar*¹⁶

¹² Double sided percussion instrument struck with sticks.

¹³ Punjab traditional dance.

¹⁴ The genre of *dhadi* involves the narration of the deeds of martyrs and heroes through song. Associated with the Punjab, the genre is mostly performed by Sikh musicians during religious rituals and events. The *dhadi* group consists of three musicians, two of whom play the *dhad* – a small, double-sided, hourglass-shaped drum made of wood – and one who plays the *sarangi* – an instrument with three strings rubbed with a bow and numerous other sympathetic strings. In the Sikh tradition, there is an additional member of the group who acts as a narrator.

¹⁵ Performers of *kirtan*, Sikh sacred music.

¹⁶ Symbol and expression of the monotheistic foundation of Sikhism.

FIGURE 2. Devotees on black Royal Enfield motorcycles, with an Italian flag and a Sikh flag. *Nagar kirtan* in Brescia, April 20, 2019. Photo by the author.

symbols, and images of Guru Gobind Singh, the tenth Guru who led the community. The *panj pyare*,¹⁷ together with a group of devotees, manage the movement of the *Guru Granth Sahib*, accompanied by the *ardas* prayer¹⁸ and the invocation *WaheGuru*, Praise the Guru. To get a better view of the main float carrying the *Guru Granth Sahib* and to witness this sacred moment, I take off my shoes and move closer. The sound of the prayers is minimal, even though the *granthi* – the custodian of the temple who often leads the ritual – is using a microphone; the entire space is saturated with Punjabi music, the beat of the *dhol*, and the voices of the large crowd.

Finally, something happens. It is almost 2 p.m. Floats, cars and devotees began to move. The local police, who had already closed the roads, remain in place to manage vehicular traffic. *Bole So Nihal*¹⁹ is called from the lead float, and everyone answer, *Sat Sri Akal*.²⁰ Two devotees on shiny black Royal Enfield motorcycles, flying an Italian flag and a Sikh flag, take their places at the head of the procession, rev their engines, and the procession begins to move (Fig. 2).

¹⁷ The “five beloved” disciples representing the first five Sikhs who underwent the *khalsa* ceremony in 1699. The *Panj Pyare* are baptized Sikhs who march barefoot carrying swords or, in many of the *nagar kirtan* in the diaspora where swords are banned, flags of Sikhism.

¹⁸ Prayer of supplication, recited before or after an important event, to ask God for support and help.

¹⁹ The first part of the statement can be translated as *whoever utters [the following statement] will be blessed*.

²⁰ The second part of the statement can be translated as *God is the truth*.

FIGURE 3. Young men playing the *nagara* and sharing in real time on social media. *Nagar kirtan* in Brescia, April 20, 2019. Photo by the author.

Behind the motorcycles is a black pick-up truck carrying the *nagara*, the large drum beaten with sticks that announces the arrival of the procession. The truck is also equipped with a large screen displaying video clips of sacred music and a powerful sound system blasting Punjabi music. Two young men play the *nagara* with energy, while simultaneously sharing Facebook videos and Instagram stories on their smartphones. Immediately behind the pick-up truck, local *gatka*, martial art groups parade, offering spectacular demonstrations of their martial art, accompanied by recorded music (Fig. 3). They are followed by a long line of cars and SUVs decorated with flowers and religious symbols, but also with turbaned dolls and puppets.

I settled on a street corner with a good view of the procession as it passes. I hear the *nagara*, then the recorded music; I am almost overwhelmed by the sheer volume of sound and the number of people, which I still cannot quantify. I observe religious symbols, ritual movements and gestures, and *gatka* performances without swords, only with the spectacular *chakkar*, an accessory for martial arts performances.

Women and men parade in both traditional and modern dress; it is a riot of selfies, videos and live-streaming. The procession continues with devotees sweeping the street with brooms and singing the invocation *Sat Nam WaheGuru*, God is the true name, before the passage of the *Guru Granth Sahib*. This invocation, however, remains muffled, blending with both the recorded and the live music played by the *dhadi* ensemble on the first float following the *Guru Granth Sahib*.

FIGURE 4. The main float carrying the *Guru Granth Sahib*. *Nagar kirtan* in Brescia, April 20, 2019. Photo by the author.

The street cleaning is then completed by a tanker truck that sprays water along the entire route. The main float is preceded by the *panj pyare*, devotees with traditional dresses walking with flags of Sikhism (Fig. 4).

The head of the procession is followed by smaller floats. They are carrying a professional *dhadi* group, with two *dhad* players, one of whom is also a singer, a *sarangi* player and a narrator, a professional *kirtaniya* group – with two *harmoniums* and a *tabla* – alternating with local performers. There are also children holding balloons printed with the date of the event, as well as floats distributing food and drink. We walk for miles, accompanied by the non-stop performances of *dhadi* and *kirtaniya* groups (Fig. 5).

The long stretch through Brescia's industrial area is particularly evocative. The urban landscape, made up of industrial warehouses and factories, is transformed by the passage of the Sikhs into a sacred place, but also into a place of leisure and economic exchange, with stalls set up by travel agencies, phone companies and bus rental services. Indian food and drinks are offered along the route – but also ice cream and pizza, to please everyone. Crossing the long road underpass is an incredible experience: a wild mixture of sounds, noises, voices and music creates a thunderous echo.

According to the newspapers, there are 35,000 people. I feel as though I'm witnessing something magnificent, and I can hardly believe I'm in Brescia. The parks and green areas around me are filled with Indian families, joining or leaving the procession in a com-

FIGURE 5. *Kirtaniya* group performing on a float. *Nagar kirtan* in Brescia, April 20, 2019. Photo by the author.

pletely spontaneous and unstructured way. A float full of children waving balloons and Italian flags passes by; a large peace flag is draped across the side. Behind me, at the very end of the procession, a group of young men – led by a sharply dressed figure wearing teardrop Ray-Bans, a neatly trimmed beard, and a headscarf instead of the traditional turban – shout pro-Khalistan slogans.²¹

We arrive in Piazzale Bruno Beccaria, which has been transformed from a vast parking lot into a small window onto Punjab, or perhaps into an intermediate space between Punjab and Italy. Flower petals are dropped from a helicopter that circles the square several times. Food and clothing stalls, along with children's games, fill much of the square. Recorded music blares from the cars and the *dhol* player begins to play again. From the stage set up for the occasion, representatives of the city administration and of the *Gurdwaras* greet the participants. Their speeches are followed by prayers and *kirtan* performances by musicians from the Golden Temple. Devotees sit cross-legged, eyes closed, on the vast carpet spread out before the stage, listening in ecstatic reverence.

The procession comes to a stop, and the celebration begins.

²¹ The boys are referring to the Khalistan Zindabar Force (KZF) group, which wants to create an independent Sikh homeland.

FIGURE 6. The Sikh crowd at the *nagar kirtan*. Brescia, April 20, 2019. Photo by the author.

3. The *nagar kirtan*: a rite in motion

Within Sikh communities, both in the homeland and in the diaspora, it is common to celebrate events and anniversaries with religious processions. The procession is called *nagar kirtan*; *nagar* means city or neighborhood, *kirtan* refers to the practice of religious music.²² This expression can be rendered in English as “town praising” or “singing in town”, expressions that immediately bring us closer to the deeper meaning of this rite. The main themes are those of movement and of the city, understood as a place other than the temple, but above all that of singing, the concrete and metaphorical appropriation of urban space through prayers expressed in song and sound. There is no specific time of year for processions; anniversaries in Sikh history or in the life of a community may be celebrated in this way. However, the most widely celebrated event in any part of the world is Vaisakhi, which falls on April 13 or 14, the day on which, according to tradition, the tenth Guru, Gobind Singh, founded the *khalsa*, the community of initiated Sikhs, in 1699.

²² For an in-depth study of history, structure, and the social context of the procession see Singh 2023.

3.1 A description of the rite

For the *nagar kirtan*, the *Guru Granth Sahib* is taken out of the temple and transported to the site of the procession. In the Italian diaspora, the *Gurdwaras* are often located in peripheral areas, far from major population centers. For this reason, communities typically choose to hold the processions in nearby cities where there is a significant public presence.

An analysis of the morphology of *nagar kirtan* reveals that several core elements are consistently present and fundamental to the procession: the *Guru Granth Sahib*, the *panj pyare*, the *sangat*, and sacred music. The arrival of the *nagar kirtan* is often (though not always) announced by the rhythms of the *nagara*. The road is meticulously cleaned with brooms and water by members of the *sangat*, and is sometimes sprinkled with flower petals. Traffic is halted to allow the smooth passage of the procession. The *panj pyare* lead the parade, followed by devotees in traditional attire. Behind them comes the main float, draped and richly decorated, carrying the *Guru Granth Sahib*, and then the *sangat*, chanting religious hymns. Musical performances vary: the devotional chants of the participants overlap with performances by professional or semi-professional *kirtaniya*, *dhadi*, and *kavishri* groups.²³

The structure of the procession described in the introduction corresponds to general patterns, though the number of floats varies depending on the size of the event. A stage, either well-structured or improvised, is usually set up at the departure and arrival points of the procession. In front of it, the devotees sit, replicating the *darbar* space, the prayer room of the *Gurdwara*, to listen to musical performances, prayers, and institutional speeches.

The core elements of the procession are framed by a number of variable components that make the *nagar kirtan* either lavish and spectacular or intimate and understated. These include the presence or absence of decorated floats, the variety of musical performers, recorded music broadcast from multiple sound sources, market stalls, planes scattering flower petals, television screens or other technological devices, and particular attention paid to non-Sikh spectators. Flags – whether of peace, Sikhism, Khalistan, or the host countries – as well as slogans chanted by pro-Khalistan groups, references to key historical events in Sikhism, and the presence of both sacred and secular symbols, can all be observed and interpreted within the context of the procession.

Preparations for *nagar kirtan* begin many months in advance. The *Gurdwara*'s administrative council manages and oversees the organization, delegating specific tasks to various internal subgroups. These may include obtaining permits from local authorities, handling security concerns, arranging *langar*, the collective and free kitchen, supplies, selecting musical groups to invite, managing media relations, and coordinating the setup of floats.

²³ A genre in the form of sung poetry, without instrumental accompaniment, narrating events that occurred in the history of Sikhism with a specific vocal style.

3.2 The *nagar kirtan* as a rite

A rite, according to a definition adopted by Victor Turner in 1979, is characterized by the constant presence of metalanguage, codes and expressions that allow participants and spectators to share in the experience. As the author notes, «[t]he languages by which a group communicates with itself are not, of course, limited to speech codes: they include gestures, music, dance, graphic representation, painting, sculpture, and the making of symbolic objects. They are dramatic, literally “doing” codes» (Turner 1979: 467). This definition is easily applied to *nagar kirtan*, which, to be shared and understood by the entire community, must retain several ritual elements and gestures unchanged. The *nagar kirtan* can be described as a journey of the *Guru Granth Sahib* outside the *Gurdwara*, spreading its words through the streets of the cities it passes through by chanting the hymns it contains.

The central role of the *Guru Granth Sahib* in religious processions is articulated by Kristina Myrvold in her essay on Sikh *nagar kirtan* in India:

An analysis of contemporary Sikh procession in India will demonstrate the centrality of the *Guru Granth Sahib*, in religious performances. The ritual acts and regal symbols used in solemnized transportations of the *Guru Granth Sahib*, and processions like *Nagar Kirtan* in which the *Guru Granth Sahib* plays a significant role, are not merely means to symbolically represent the spiritual superiority of the scripture. The arrangement of spaces and ritualized acts in any procession that involves moving the *Guru Granth Sahib* can be viewed as strategies by which participants invest the scripture with the agency and authority of a *Guru*. Within the framework of an enduring social relationship to the *Guru*-scripture, disciples personify the text and treat it as a social being who is present in and interacting with the world. (Myrvold 2008: 141)

The author bases much of her work on the study of the role assigned to the *Guru Granth Sahib*, which is experienced by the Sikh community not as a mere object, but as the personification of the object itself. The procession would thus be a strategy to reinforce his real and concrete presence as a living being. As she specifies:

The mode of transporting the scripture exemplifies the religious strategies by which Sikhs attempt to surmount the difference between a mere “book” and a text attributed the agency of a *Guru*. The scripture is publicly displayed as a ‘person’ of superior status requiring honourable ministrations. To religious Sikhs the careful ministrations to the Sikh scripture are acts of reverence and devotion to the *Guru* who enables devotees to establish relationships with the invisible supreme God. The *Guru* who shows the way to the path of liberation should be served and honoured in the best possible way. (*Ibidem*: 148)

As Massimo Leone points out, the procession sacralizes places that are outside the temple, giving the faithful a sense of enlargement of the sacred space and a percep-

tion of the omnipresence of the divine, no longer confined to the interior of a place of worship.

On the one hand, these rituals succeed in congregating several individual agencies [...] thus helping them to obliterate the boundary between the sacred environment of the place of worship and the profane environment of the space surrounding it. Consequently, in religious processions subjects experience an enlargement of the environment of the sacred that encourages them to believe in its omnipresence, in the reassuring idea that their entire existence takes place (literally and metaphorically) under the protection of transcendence. (Leone 2014: 315)

A rite is a specific situation in which events unfold and time and space are transformed. Time refers not only to the actual duration of the procession, but also to the time structured by the sequence of ritual actions, the rhythm of the walking pace, and the tempo of devotional music. Similarly, space encompasses both the physical streets and roads through which the procession moves, and the symbolic space that evokes and transforms another, geographically distant, place. Music plays a key role in enabling and shaping this transformation.

One of the key concepts developed by Turner is that of liminality. By *liminality*, the author refers to a state of limbo; a transitional phase in which individuals or groups are no longer in their previous state, but have not yet reached the next: «[t]his term, literally “being-on-a-threshold,” means a state or process that lies between the normal, everyday cultural and social states and processes of getting and spending, maintaining law and order, and registering structural status» (Turner 1979: 465). Individuals in liminal space and time are called *communitas*, a community in which individuals are equal, completely separated from the status criteria adopted in everyday life. Liminality and *communitas* generate cognitive and affective capacities that are normally constrained by specific social position; liminality is thus the optimal scenario of relational experience. Participants in pilgrimage and procession often undergo this sense of *communitas*, situated between a ritual “framing process” and the highly subjective dimension of individual experience.²⁴

In *nagar kirtan*, a fixed structure composed of highly symbolic elements provides the ritual frame. At the same time, the procession remains malleable, shaped by the individual experiences of participants and their relationship to the place and broader social context. Music in *nagar kirtan* plays a key role not only in recreating and reinforcing a sense of internal community, but also – perhaps more importantly – in enabling a different kind of engagement and interaction with the surrounding society.

²⁴ On this topic also Cassio 2019.

3.3 The *nagar kirtan* in diaspora

Nagar kirtan in the diaspora strengthens the sense of belonging to Sikhism and allows the entire *sangat* to experience a sense of *communitas*. This requires educating younger generations about practices and appropriate behaviors, often through negotiation and compromise. The procession becomes the vehicle of a collective memory (Khurana 2011: 228-229), even for those who may not share a personal or direct memory. Quoting Ahmed, «[t]he very failure of individual memory is compensated for by collective memory» (Ahmed 1999: 330). For many participants, the procession is experienced as a form of immersion – either in the past or in a relocated present – where time follows the rhythm of ritual, and space evokes Punjab as a mythical place of origin and reference. Devotees with diverse interests and sensibilities can nonetheless find a shared sense of belonging to a common space that is both real and, above all, symbolic. The procession is a highly standardized expression of identity, aiming to display the most significant features of Sikh religious and cultural belonging.

The public performance of *nagar kirtan* in urban settings also enables Sikhs to be recognized by the local population, to assert their visibility and claim acknowledgment within wider society (Myrvold 2008: 152), thereby making their presence in the territory more visible and meaningful. Indeed, religious festivals in the diaspora are public events that relate directly to a territory and its inhabitants (Kumar 2008: 209). For this reason, processions are often held in central and densely populated areas of cities, despite the logistical constraints that this may entail.

Moreover, *nagar kirtan* offers an opportunity for community members to build connections and engage in dialogue with the places in which they live. It becomes a “cultural spectacle” (Hirvi 2013: 126), where national flags of host countries, prayers translated into the local language, and a variety of other elements addressed to the broader public carry significant meaning. Non-Sikhs are not merely spectators: they play an active role in shaping new relational dynamics between culturally distinct worlds.

The sounds of *nagar kirtan*

I have highlighted the sound elements present in the procession as follows, assigning each an abbreviation used in Table 1.

On a spatial level, sound sources tend to occupy preferred, though not fixed, positions within the procession. Each musical element can be seen as a building block of the overall sonic event that is *nagar kirtan*. The way these blocks are combined, their presence or absence, and their spatial arrangement allow the procession to take on different meanings.

One recurring element in all the documented processions is the invocation *Sat Nam WabeGuru* (SW), repeated like a *mantra*. When it is initiated and accompanied by musicians on the floats – with *harmonium*, *tabla*, *dholak*, or *chimta*²⁵ – it is sung collectively

²⁵ Long, flat piece of steel or iron that is pointed at both ends and folded over in the middle. A

SW	Intonation of <i>Sat Nam WaheGuru</i> (God is the real name) from the <i>sangat</i> (the community of believers) – “necessary fundamental sound”
N	Rhythms performed on the <i>nagara</i> (the large drum beaten with sticks)
RMO	Recorded music at the opening of the <i>nagar kirtan</i>
RMG	Recorded music for <i>gatka</i> (martial art) demonstrations
KI	Professional or amateur <i>kirtaniya</i> (<i>kirtan</i> group)
D	Professional or amateur <i>dhadi</i> (group composed of two dhad players and one sarangi player)
KA	Professional or amateur <i>kavishri</i> (sung poetry performance)
O	Other musicians, not necessarily related to religious music
DC	Devotional chants sung by the <i>sangat</i>
PK	Pro-Khalistan anthems and slogans

TABLE 1. Sound elements of the *nagar kirtan*.

and simultaneously by the entire *sangat*. At other times, however, the invocation emerges independently from small groups of devotees, in a more fragmented and spontaneous manner, without musical accompaniment. These spontaneous intonations contribute to the shifting, multilayered soundscape of the procession, alternating between moments of unified chanting and dispersed devotional expression. When a musical performance on a float comes to an end, what follows is never silence. What remains is this foundational sonic presence: a moving, continuous invocation that sustains the spiritual energy of the *nagar kirtan*.

The second key sound element, the *nagara* (N), acts as a signal that symbolically marks the beginning of the procession and defines the boundary between the sacred space of the ritual and the secular, external world. Traditionally used as a war drum to announce the advance of soldiers into battle, the *nagara* in the context of *nagar kirtan* serves to sonically demarcate sacred space. Positioned at the head of the procession, the *nagara* primarily functions as an outward-facing sound: it announces the presence and movement of the *nagar kirtan* to the surrounding environment rather than addressing the procession internally. Its powerful, resonant sound can be heard from a distance, signaling the arrival of the sacred event.

The use of recorded music at the opening of the procession (RMO) has become a common trend in many *nagar kirtan* events in recent years. As revealed in numerous interviews with participants and organizers, there is a widely shared belief within the Sikh community that the procession should be musically defined by prayers and ritual invocations. However, many organizers prefer to place loudspeakers near the front of the procession that play highly rhythmic religious music. This music, together with the sound of the *nagara*, marks the beginning of the *nagar kirtan* and makes it audible from afar, acoustically announcing its presence. It overlaps with the “basic sound” of the rite,

metal ring is attached near the fold, and there are jingles or rings attached along the sides at regular intervals.

which is highly symbolic and devotional, creating a sonic association between festive energy and sacred intention. The music is often a mix of tracks composed specifically for the event, similar to those used in *gatka* demonstrations (RMG). Stylistically, it can be compared to early 2000s electronic dance music, particularly in its use of rhythmic ostinato patterns, heavy bass lines, and timbral choices that include distorted synth bass sounds. This electronic instrumentation is frequently combined with sounds that evoke a “traditional” sonic world, including digital string instrument samples, which help conjure images of Sikh warriors and inspire the journey. The music used for *gatka* performances is often the same or very similar to the opening music. In some cases, the sound is emitted from a single source; in others, it is broadcast from an additional float positioned after the *nagara* or at the rear of the procession.

The choice to include *kirtaniya* (KI), *dhadi* (D), and/or *kavishri* (KA) performers in *nagar kirtan* processions depends on several factors, including the availability of these groups, economic considerations, and varying degrees of intentionality regarding the level of spectacularity attributed to the procession and the role assigned to music within it. *Kirtan*, as sacred music, is ideally performed on the main float carrying the *Guru Granth Sahib*. Multiple *kirtan* groups may be present, and in some cases, children are also invited to perform on a separate float. However, some organizers opt for *dhadi* and *kavishri* ensembles instead, due to their greater sonic impact and the perception that the music they perform is more immediately accessible and appreciable by the broader congregation of devotees.²⁶

I observed only a limited presence of performers playing “accessory” musical instruments (O), not strictly associated with religious music. Exceptions include a *dhhol* player in Brescia, and, on a few occasions, performers of the *shankh* (conch shell) and *ransingha*, the long traditional trumpets.

By devotional chants (DC) I refer to all songs collectively sung by devotees, often a cappella or accompanied by musical instruments. The lyrics are devotional or express thanksgiving, drawing from *shabads* and ritual formulas found in *Guru Granth Sahib* or in the *Dasam Granth*.²⁷ These chants constitute a shared musical repertoire familiar to most members of the community, who actively participate in the singing.

The final element I have included in the table is the intonation of pro-Khalistan (PK) slogans. I recorded this sonic presence only during the processions in Cremona and Brescia processions, where numerous Khalistan flags were also waved.

²⁶ *Kirtan* consists in the musical rendering of verses from the *Guru Granth Sahib* in Gurmukhi, a liturgical language that combines elements from multiple linguistic traditions and is often not fully understood by the broader Sikh community, particularly by younger generations or those born and raised outside of Punjab. In contrast, *dhadi* and *kavishri* performances typically employ more accessible forms of Punjabi, making their narratives and messages easier to grasp and emotionally engaging for a wider audience.

²⁷ Scripture containing *shabads* from the tenth Guru.

4.1 Sound Levels and Overlaps

The acoustic elements I have just described are combined in different ways to create the sonic sense of each *nagar kirtan*. With the illustration in figure 7, I intend to graphically depict the *nagar kirtan* with a linear representation, showing the procession as a straight line with a beginning (top of the page) and an end (bottom of the page). The graphic representation is necessarily fictitious, an abstract model of an ideal procession in which all the sound elements that I have clearly listed are simultaneously present and coexist. Figure 8 indicates, through colors, the sound levels that I assign to each musical element of the procession. The straight line at the base of the drawing virtually indicates the procession as if it were fully unfolded before us, with a beginning spatially delimited by the float with the *nagara* and an end defined by the last worshippers. I have used acronyms to indicate the various elements that become sound sources from which the many sounds propagate. The colors used for the concentric circles, with which I wanted to represent the propagation of sound waves, indicate the intensity of the sounds: in the various shades of red are the loudest sounds, in yellow are the sounds of medium intensity, and in light blue are the weakest sounds. The transition between loud sounds and medium intensity sounds is orange, and the transition between medium intensity sounds and the weakest sounds is green. The sound intensity I assign to each element is an average of the intensities I encountered, and in most cases it remains constant. As can be seen, some sounds extend before and after the actual end of the procession, and many of them overlap in several positions. The *mantra Sat Nam WabeGuru* (SW) has the same intensity in every area of the procession, forming a sound structure that is clearly audible when all other elements are not present. The most intense sounds are those used in the opening of the procession: the *nagara* (N) and the recorded music of the opening (RMO) and the accompanying *gatka* (RMG) really characterize and define the procession. The *kirtanias* (KI) usually have a medium intensity sound. The performances of the *dhadi* (D) and *kavishri* (KA) tend to be more audible than those of the *kirtaniya* (KI). The pro-Khalistan (PK) slogans, although done without the amplification, still acoustically defines a fairly large area.

It is worth noting that when multiple sound elements converge, the most intense ones – represented in red – tend to dominate. Conversely, when fewer sounds are present, even the lower-intensity ones – depicted in light blue – can be easily perceived (Figg. 7 and 8).

5. The *nagar kirtan* of Cremona

The annual Vaisakhi procession in Cremona²⁸ attracts devotees from various locations. Initiated in 2009, the decision to hold the celebration in the city rather than at the *Gurdwara* located in Pessina Cremonese, approximately 25 km away, was driven by the desire

²⁸ A municipality in southern Lombardy, on the Po River, with about 72,000 inhabitants. I followed religious processions in Cremona from 2015 to 2019, and I have video recordings of less recent procession.

FIGURE 7. The sound elements of the *nagar kirtan*. Illustration by Alessandra Belloni.

over the years in relation to a changing attitude toward the city and its inhabitants, transforming them from passive spectators into active participants.

In recent years, the route of the procession has remained unchanged, crossing the small city from one side to the other. The procession starts from a large parking area near

FIGURE 8. The sounds of the *nagar kirtan*. Diagram by Melissa Fontana.

to engage a broader public and to introduce the Sikh community to local Italian residents. Although the Sikh presence in the province has historically been concentrated in rural areas, the procession has played a significant role in making the community more visible in the urban context. Today, the *nagar kirtan* has become a well-established event that draws not only Sikh devotees but also Italians with an interest in Indian culture, Kundalini Yoga practitioners, and the simply curious. On a musical level, the *nagar kirtan* in Cremona illustrates how musical choices have evolved

the Municipal Stadium and proceeds toward a large park along the Po River, unfolding along streets just outside the historic city center, which remains inaccessible due to traffic regulations and is unsuitable for such a large number of participants. Both the departure and arrival points provide ample space for stages used for musical performances and prayers, as well as for food stalls, clothing and spice vendors, children's games, and even tour operators offering special deals for trips to India. This strategic choice allows the Sikh community to express its culture through music while simultaneously engaging the urban environment and fostering an atmosphere of celebration and exchange.

From 2009 to the present, the *nagar kirtan* in Cremona has remained stable in its structural components, yet variations in its sonic configuration have conveyed evolving messages over the years. While some musical choices may be circumstantial or dictated by logistical considerations, many appear to be the result of deliberate decisions, as confirmed through conversations with devotees, organizers, and musicians. A diachronic analysis of Sikh processions in Cremona reveals an ongoing negotiation between the internal needs of the community – including generational differences and varying levels of religious involvement – and the desire to capture external attention. This results in musical selections that aim to resonate broadly, accommodating diverse expectations and sensibilities.

In 2009, when devotees did not yet have a permanent place of worship and gathered in small groups in farmsteads and private homes, the primary goal of the community was to establish itself economically and to secure a sacred space in which to collectively express their faith. The *nagar kirtan* that year was primarily characterized by devotional chants and *kirtan*, reflecting a form of popular religiosity that appeared strongly oriented toward internal cohesion and community affirmation. Nonetheless, the procession opened with pro-Khalistan slogans. According to Jaspreet Singh, this choice was rather unplanned: a group of men positioned at the front of the procession began chanting these slogans without fully considering their sonic impact beyond the internal space of the procession.

I was there in 2009, I had already been in Italy for a while, I was 17 at the time. I knew little about Sikhism, just what my mom told me and the prayers that they taught me that I had to recite in the morning and at night before bed. For the *nagar kirtan* they made me dress nicely and we all went together. We sang the prayers that my mom always sang at home. I remember at the beginning of the *nagar kirtan* there were these men yelling, but it wasn't until a few years later that I wondered why. I remember at the procession an Italian lady approached me and asked, somewhat intimidated "why are those men shouting so much? Who are they protesting against? Am I at a protest march?". From there I realized that we were not presenting ourselves in Cremona in the right way, the Italians were intimidated, I had to change something (Conversation with Jaspreet Singh, Cremona, May 2, 2020).

Over time, the growing awareness of the presence of spectators outside the Sikh community – curious to learn more about the event – appears to have contributed to changes in

the structure of the procession, with increasing attention paid to the symbolic meanings conveyed by its various elements, including music. Parallel to this outward-facing shift, the construction of the *Gurdwara* in Pessina Cremonese and the launch of the first youth-oriented activities marked a significant phase in the internal consolidation of the community, particularly in the realm of intergenerational education. One notable change has been the decision to open the procession with recorded music and modern electronic sounds, a choice that has been well received by both Sikh youth and the Italian public. This is not an innovation unique to Cremona: similar musical strategies are commonly employed in other Italian cities and in various contexts across the Sikh diaspora. What is particularly interesting is to explore the motivations behind such a musical solution and the multiple meanings it may carry in terms of identity, outreach, and generational dialogue:

We used to open the *nagar kirtan* with *nagara* and our own religious songs, which are still there and are important. Unfortunately, Italians didn't like that music, they run away, they were bored and didn't understand. So, we decide to use this music that is very similar to what the Italians listen to, it's modern music, they like it, and so they can't wait for *the nagar kirtan* to come through. You have to try to please everybody (Conversation with Gursharan Singh, Cremona, April 18, 2015).

This type of music appears to resonate particularly with young Sikhs who, while acknowledging the importance of what they refer to as “traditional *kirtan*,” tend to prefer listening to this “new music.” As a result, each *nagar kirtan* seems to oscillate between the use of musically “correct” forms – those perceived as religiously appropriate or authentic – and more appealing or contemporary sounds. The procession thus becomes a space of negotiation, where a balance is sought between different aesthetic and generational preferences in an effort to satisfy a diverse audience:

I know very well that we should not use this music, but I like this modern music. I listen to it at home when I'm studying, when I'm running, when I'm cleaning. It energizes me, it makes me feel happy. And I like to listen to it here, loudly. I am sorry that there is not so much traditional *kirtan*, but it is boring (Conversation with Inderjit Kaur, Cremona, April 13, 2019).

The 2017 procession appeared particularly balanced, juxtaposing high-intensity musical elements – such as loud, amplified music framing the event – with low-intensity, introspective music at the heart of the procession. This structure seems to reflect a conscious negotiation between internal and external expectations. Similarly, the decision to move *gatka* performances from the end to the beginning of the procession was reportedly made to capture the attention of the Italian public. Although contested by some members of

the *sangat*, the choice was rooted in a desire to be welcoming and communicative toward the host society.

In contrast, the 2018 procession was characterized by the absence of high-volume or music-intensive elements. The sonic space was entirely filled with devotional chanting, signaling, according to many devotees, a deliberate search for a more intimate and prayerful atmosphere.

The reappearance of pro-Khalistan slogans in 2019, this time at the end of the procession, seemed to carry little actual political intent and instead functioned as a spectacular element. In conversation, M.S., one of the participants, revealed a somewhat performative and uncritical attitude toward the chanting:

THEA: Did you chant like this throughout the *nagar kirtan*?

M.S.: Yes, we follow our leader

THEA: What do these chants refer to?

M.S.: To Khalistan.

THEA: but can you explain more, what does this Khalistan consist of? What do you mean by these slogans?

M.S. (laughing): Don't exaggerate, so we go into too much detail. In *nagar kirtan* these things are chanted, we also chant them (Conversation with M.S., Cremona, April 13, 2019).

This group of young men appeared to have made a conscious choice to become a disruptive sonic presence within the procession, drawing attention to themselves through the performance of a politically charged, though ambiguously articulated, theme. Their actions highlight the role of sound not only as a form of devotion, but also as a vehicle for self-display and symbolic contestation.

In the second *nagar kirtan* of 2019, held in honor of Guru Nanak, a *kirtan* group took a central role. According to Damanjot Singh, son of the *granthi* of the Pessina Cremonese *Gurdwara*, the inclusion of *kirtan* for this particular occasion was deliberate. While many devotees would have preferred the more energetic rhythms of *dhadi*, the organizers chose to honor the founder of the Sikh religion with what they considered the most appropriate and respectful musical form. In this context, *kirtan* reasserted itself as the structural and connotative sound of a procession primarily addressed to the internal community. Such decisions, however, are rarely neutral. They reflect a broader system of internal negotiation between the general *sangat* and the organizing committee – often composed of elders and authoritative members of the *Gurdwara* – who oversee not only the logistical aspects of the event but also its symbolic and sonic coherence. Musical choices, in this sense, can be read as outcomes of a form of *sonic self-regulation*, or even self-censorship, aimed at constructing a representation of the community deemed appropriate for both internal edification and external visibility. This often leads to tension or disagreement, especially

when the expressive desires of specific subgroups – such as youth or more politically motivated individuals – do not align with the vision of the organizers.

This negotiation becomes particularly evident when examining the reappearance of pro-Khalistan slogans in the same year. In contrast to 2009, when the chants occurred at the very start of the procession, in 2019 the slogans were shouted from the rear, physically and symbolically occupying a liminal position. The chanting was not coordinated with the organizing committee, and many participants reacted with visible discomfort, distancing themselves physically. No intervention was made to silence them, however, suggesting both the limited control that the organizers are able – or willing – to exert over the entire soundscape of the procession, and a tacit tolerance toward this type of performative excess, as long as it remains marginal in space and time. In this case, the sonic intervention appeared to be more of a disruptive act than a true political statement. In this sense, the political nature of the slogans was ambiguous. Rather than articulating a coherent ideological position, the chants seemed to function primarily as a form of spectacular display – an attempt to mark presence and assert identity, perhaps more toward peers and observers than as a statement of political activism.

These sonic tensions between prescribed and spontaneous, authorized and marginal, devotional and political reveal the *nagar kirtan* not only as a site of ritual cohesion, but also as a stage for negotiation, contestation, and change. Music, in this sense, becomes not just a vehicle for collective expression, but also a field in which divergent voices and generational differences emerge and are (more or less) accommodated. The soundscape of the procession thus tells us as much about unity as it does about the multiplicity and evolving complexity of Sikh life in diaspora.

6. Conclusion: Places and Sounds

Nagar kirtan is an essential part of Sikh celebrations, and its meaning acquires further depth in the diasporic context. The religious procession allows individuals to reconnect with their identity and territorial roots, «[t]he Guru, personified as King, makes his way through the city inspiring Sikhs to stay devoted and reenforcing the supremacy of the Guru over the world» (Singh 2023: 112). Popular devotion is accompanied by forms of political expression that refer both to the homeland – as in the case of the “No Farmers No Food”²⁹ protest movement, which in 2020 appeared in many Italian processions with appeals for economic and political support, or the more controversial issue of Khalistan – and to diasporic demands, such as the right to carry the *kirpan*.³⁰

²⁹ On 27 November 2020 farmers from the regions Haryana, Western Uttar Pradesh and Punjab marched to Delhi, beginning what would become one of the world’s biggest protests. For over four months farmers in India have been protesting the Indian Agriculture Acts of 2020 passed by Prime Minister Modi.

³⁰ A curved, single-edged blade that *khalsa* Sikhs are required to wear as part of their religious uniform, as prescribed by the Sikh Code of Conduct.

In the diaspora, *nagar kirtan* becomes a vehicle through which Sikhs demonstrate devotion but also claim public recognition. Each community, depending on its location and local context, organizes a procession that “works”: one that seeks to satisfy a plural audience, both Sikh and non-Sikh (Facci 2019). Ancillary elements of the ritual – motorcycles, flower decorations, helicopters, balloons, Italian and peace flags displayed alongside Sikh flags, the distribution of both Indian and Italian food, booths offering free literature in Italian, commercial stands, and large screens projecting translations of sacred text – should be read in this light: as tools for engagement, visibility, and dialogue. In this sense, sound plays a central and inherently political role. More than a medium of devotion, the soundscape of the *nagar kirtan* shapes the collective experience of the event. The *Guru Granth Sahib*, a text composed entirely in verse meant to be sung, defines the ritual core, but the overall sonic environment is far more complex. The processions studied in Brescia and Cremona illustrate how multiple layers of sound – from sacred hymns to electronic music, from drumming to street noise – coexist and interact to create an immersive ritual space. If the Cremona *nagar kirtan* appears more musically “conservative,” it would be reductive to describe it only in terms of genre or repertoire. What truly matters is the quality, intensity, distribution, and overlap of sounds, and how these sonic choices reflect tensions and negotiations within the community.

Following Turner, it is precisely this sensorial and performative complexity that enables the emergence of *communitas*: not as a homogeneous or static unity, but as a dynamic field where identities, expectations, and generational values are negotiated. The ritual generates temporary spaces of suspension and transformation: liminal zones in which sound plays a central role in binding individuals together, even amid difference. The case of Brescia exemplifies this well. There, the soundscape is divided into two main blocks: the first consists of recorded music and the *nagara* before the appearance of the *Guru Granth Sahib*, designed to announce the procession and draw attention; the second includes live performances of *kirtan*, *dhadi*, *kavishri*, and collective chanting, which envelops the *sangat* during the walk. The use of rhythmic, danceable recorded music at the beginning – while contested by some – was intended to appeal to both Sikh youth and Italian spectators. In the words of one organizer, the goal was to create a shared public celebration, “a party open to all.”

Similar strategies were employed in Bolzano, where the Sikh presence is more recent. The decision to offer pizza instead of Indian food, to broadcast Italian translations via loudspeakers, and to include a voiceover narrating the meaning of the procession during the walk, all reflect a strong desire to be understood by the host society. Yet even there, tensions emerged: youth disagreed over the prominence of electronic dance music in the opening section, expressing a longing for a more traditional sound centered on *kirtan*:

I always listen to this music [electronic dance music] at home or in the car. But I don't agree with opening the *nagar kirtan* like that, only the *nagara* and the recitation of the

prayer should be used along with the *kirtan*. We had to choose, and since many of us like this music, they decided to use it. And then they thought that the young people in Bolzano would like it too, because they don't understand the words and they don't know that it's religious, but the music is the same as what my friends listen to. Luckily, in the middle of the procession, there was still the *kirtan* that has to be played (Conversation with Fateh Singh, April 28, 2019).

The spectacular *gatka* demonstrations, accompanied by the same electronic dance music, were also repositioned to the beginning of the event, while politically sensitive elements, such as pro-Khalistan slogans, were relegated to the end, physically and symbolically marginal.

In smaller towns with fewer Italian spectators – such as Fiorenzuola (PC), Casalmaggiore (CR), and Cortemaggiore (PC) – the processions tend to preserve a more intimate, devotional atmosphere. They often begin with the *nagara* alone, with no recorded music, and are dominated by collectively sung hymns. Still, even in these contexts, the processions become louder and more performative near central locations where the presence of non-Sikh onlookers increases, further proof that sonic choices are shaped by context, intention, and perceived audience.

In conclusion, the study of *nagar kirtan* in Italy highlights the dynamic and evolving interplay between Sikh communities and Italian society. As a musical–ritual event, the procession embodies not only devotion and memory, but also mediation, negotiation, and representation. The soundscape – complex, layered, and sometimes contradictory – is where these processes unfold most vividly. Through sound, and especially through its polyphonic tension, Sikh presence becomes visible, audible, and meaningful within the Italian public space.

Video Contents

References

- Ahmed, Sara
1999 “Home and away, narratives of migration and estrangement”, *International Journal of Cultural Studies*, II/3: 329-347.
- Bertolani, Barbara
2013 “The Sikhs In Italy: A Growing Heterogeneous and Plural Presence”, in Giuseppe Giordan and William H. Swatos (eds.), *Testing Pluralism, Globalizing Belief, Localizing Gods*, Leiden-Boston, Brill: 75-93.
2018 “Ways of making Sikhi in Italy: Considerations from a Case Study of Sikh youth”, *Sikh formations: Religion, Culture, Theory*, Routledge, XIV/3-4: 364-383.
2020 “Women and Sikhism In Theory And Practice: Normative Discourses, Seva Performances, And Agency In The Case Study Of Some Young Sikh Women In Northern Italy”, *Religions*, XI/2: <<https://doi.org/10.3390/rel11020091>>.
- Caruso, Fulvia
2022 “Emerging Thoughts from Fieldwork about Music and Migration in Cremona and its Surroundings”, in Serena Facci and Giovanni Giuriati (eds.), *Music of the Twenty-First Century Diasporas: Research and Methods*, Fondazione Giorgio Cini onlus, Venezia: 128-135.
- Cassio, Francesca
2015 “Gurbānī Sangīt: Authenticity and Influences”, *Sikh Formation: Religion, Culture, Theory*, Routledge XI/1-2: 23-60.
2023 “Singing the Scripture. Sikh Kīrtan in Literature, Practices and Musicological Studies” in Pashaura Singh and Arvind Pal Singh Mandair (eds.) *The Sikh World*, Oxon, Routledge: 312-326.
2019 “The Sonic Pilgrimage. Exploring Kīrtan and Sacred Journeying in Sikh Culture”, *Sikh formations: Religion, Culture, Theory*, Routledge, XV/1-2: 152-182.
- Denti, Domenica, Mauro Ferrari and Fabio Perocco (eds.)
2005 *I Sikh, storia e immigrazione*, Milano, FrancoAngeli.
- Facci, Serena
2009 “Funziona? Valori e usi della musica nella contemporaneità” in Francesco Giannattasio and Serena Facci (eds.), *Letnomusicologia e le musiche contemporanee. Seminario internazionale di studi 2007*, Istituto Interculturale di Studi Musicali Comparati, Fondazione Giorgio Cini onlus, <www.cini.it/it/publication/detail/5/id/1020>.
- Hirvi, Laura
2013 *Identities in Practice: A Trans-Atlantic Ethnography of Sikh Immigrants in Finland and in California*, Helsinki, Finnish Literature Society.
- Kaur, Inderjit Nilu
2018 “Transnational Affects, Transnational Worldings: Sikhs Sounding Sacred Songs, Making Multiple Worlds”, *Civilisations*, LXVII/1: 23-40.
- Khabra, Gurdeep John Singh
2012 “Music of the Sikh diaspora: devotional sounds, musical memory and cultural identity”, *Sikh formations: Religion, Culture, Theory*, VIII/2: 147-170.
- Khalsa, Nirinjan Kaur
2014 *The renaissance of Sikh devotional music. Memory, identity, orthopraxy*, PhD dissertation, Asian Language and Culture, University of Michigan.

- Khurana, Gurveen Kaur
 2011 “Home and the World, the Nagar Kirtan and Sikh Diaspora”, in Pashaura Singh (ed.) *Sikhism in Global Context*, New Delhi, Oxford University Press: 228-229.
- Kumar, Pratap P.
 2008 “Rathayatra of the Hare Krishnas in Durban: Inventing Strategies to Transmit Religious Ideas in Modern Society”, in Knut A. Jacobsen (ed.) *South Asian Religions on Display: Religious Processions in South Asia and in the Diaspora*, Oxon, Routledge: 205-216.
- Leone, Massimo
 2014 “Transcendence and Transgression in Religious Processions”, *Signs and Society*, II/2: 314-349.
- Myrvold, Kristina
 2008 “Personifying the Sikh Scripture, Ritual Processions of the Guru Granth Sahib in India” in Knut A. Jacobsen (ed.), *South Asian Religions on Display: Religious Processions in South Asia and in the Diaspora*, Oxon, Routledge: 150-156.
- Singh, Gurbeer
 2023 “The Nagar Kirtan” in Pashaura Singh and Arvind Pal Singh Mandair (eds.) *The Sikh World*, Oxon, Routledge: 102-112.
- Townsend, Charles
 2018 “Sikh Millennials of the ‘kirtan generation’ in the Making of an ‘American Sikhism’”, *Sikh formations: Religion, Culture, Theory*, XIV/3-4: 424-434.
- Turner, Victor
 1979 “Flow and Reflection: Ritual and Drama as Public Liminality”, *Japanese Journal of Religious Studies*, VI/4: 465-499.

